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AWARENESS OF ATTENTION DEFICIT HYPERACTIVITY DISORDER AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN THE PORT HARCOURT LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA

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Orcid ID: 0009000982147359 (²)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17463619>

Abstract: This study investigated the awareness of ADHD among secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. This study was guided by three specific objectives, research questions, and corresponding hypotheses. The target population comprised 3,045 teachers from public junior and senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State, which comprises 1,305 teachers of public senior secondary schools and 1,740 teachers of public junior secondary schools (Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board and Rivers State Universal Basic Education Board, 2025). A sample of 341 respondents was selected using the Taro Yamane formula. The stratified sampling technique was used to compose the sample. The “Awareness of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder Questionnaire (ADHDQ)” was validated by test and guidance counselling experts for data collection while its reliability was determined through the measure of stability using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC), which yielded a reliability index of 0.83. Out of the 341 distributed questionnaires, 330 were retrieved and analysed. Data were analysed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions, while the null hypotheses were tested using independent t-test statistics at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA demonstrated low levels of awareness regarding the core symptoms of ADHD: inattention, impulsivity, and hyperactivity. Based on the findings, it was recommended, among others, that the government and educational stakeholders should organize awareness and capacity-building programmes to equip teachers with the knowledge and classroom management strategies necessary to effectively support students with ADHD.

Keywords: Attention deficit, awareness, hyperactivity disorder; secondary school, teachers.

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INTRODUCTION

Counsellors play a vital role in facilitating students' comprehensive development and overall well-being, both as individuals and as functional members of society. Consistent guidance and psychosocial support help students cultivate appropriate, constructive, and essential behaviours for lifelong personal growth and integration into society (Ojeme, 2017). Their interventions are also critical in equipping learners with emotional resilience and social competence—qualities necessary for meaningful participation in both academic and social settings (Egbochuku & Okobia, 2021). The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN) (2014) affirms that learners are more likely to thrive when their physical, emotional, and mental well-being are nurtured adequately. This highlights the need for a stable psychological foundation, which is key to effective engagement in the learning process. Within this context, the role of the school counsellor becomes indispensable in fostering behavioural stability and mental readiness among learners.

To ensure that all categories of learners are effectively supported, it is essential that counsellors collaborate closely with teachers, who serve as the primary facilitators of learning within the school environment. This collaboration becomes even more critical within the context of inclusive education, which emphasizes the importance of accommodating all learners' diverse academic, emotional, and behavioural needs, particularly those at risk of marginalization or educational exclusion. In this regard, school counsellors play a supportive role by equipping teachers with the skills and insights necessary to identify early signs of learning difficulties and behavioural challenges (Egbule, 2024). Through this collaborative approach, counsellors not only enhance teachers' capacity to respond effectively to students' individual needs but also contribute to creating a more supportive and equitable learning environment for all students.

The importance of such support is also reflected in Nigeria's policy framework. (FRN, 2014) explicitly recognizes learning disabilities among the special educational needs categories, affirming the learners' right to appropriate services, curricula, and interventions. While attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is not mentioned in the policy, its characteristics, particularly inattention, hyperactivity, and impulsivity, fall within the broader category of "emotional and behavioural disorders." Within this policy environment, the collaboration between counsellors and teachers becomes particularly crucial.

Counsellors support teachers by helping them identify the early signs of learning difficulties and behavioural challenges. Through counselling services, behavioural assessments, and the development of individualized intervention plans, counsellors help ensure that teachers are better equipped to respond to the diverse needs of their students (Yusuf, Onifade, & Bello, 2020). This collaborative approach is especially important when addressing the needs of learners with neurodevelopmental conditions, such as attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), which often require early identification, targeted interventions, and sustained psychosocial support for optimal outcomes.

ADHD is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by persistent patterns of inattention and/or hyperactivity-impulsivity that are developmentally inappropriate and interfere with academic, social, or emotional functioning (American Psychiatric Association [APA], 2013). This interferes with a child's ability to focus, follow instructions, and appropriately regulate behavior. The symptoms are particularly disruptive in traditional classroom environments, where orderliness, sustained attention, and conformity are expected

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(Kennedy & Obumneke, 2023). Therefore, learners with ADHD require individualized instructional and behavioural support to engage meaningfully with academic content and participate constructively in school life. This underscores that ADHD is not a temporary phase but a chronic disorder that could affect a student's daily functioning and necessitates proper diagnosis and intervention. As teachers are often the first to observe students' learning and behavioural difficulties, their awareness and understanding of ADHD are essential for timely intervention, appropriate referral, and inclusive classroom practice (DuPaul, Weyandt, & Janusis, 2011).

Bhattarai, Bhusal, and Jaishi (2020) stated that ADHD begins in childhood and often persists into adulthood and is a risk factor for other mental health disorders and long-term negative outcomes, including impaired working memory abilities and ADL impairments. It also involves low academic achievement (Condo, Chan, & Kofler, 2022). Learners with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) often exhibit symptoms such as forgetfulness, excessive talking, fidgeting, and difficulty following tasks. Unfortunately, teachers sometimes misinterpret these symptoms as behavioural issues arising from poor home training, laziness, or irresponsibility, which can result in the neglect and punishment of affected students (Kennedy & Obumneke 2023). ADHD can have a broad impact on a student's life, affecting not only the child and their family but also teachers and peers, leading to disruptions in the school environment. Children with ADHD may display traits such as being overly curious, restless, impulsive, and more active than their peers. If these behaviours are not recognized, these students may become challenging for themselves, their teachers, parents, and siblings. This misinterpretation highlights the need for widespread awareness and understanding of ADHD among educators. Barkley (2016) considered the difficulties faced by a student who struggles with sitting still, maintaining focus, and speaking excessively, even when others appear less engaged. Navigating his environment daily while being expected to succeed academically presents significant challenges for such a student.

Although the exact cause of attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) remains unclear, evidence indicates that it results from a complex interplay of genetic, neurological, and environmental factors. (Hoogman, Muetzel, & Guimaraes, 2019). According to the National Health Survey (2018), genetic predisposition, abnormalities in brain structure and function, and specific perinatal conditions are all risk factors. These include premature birth (before 37 weeks of gestation), low birth weight, epilepsy, and brain injury, whether prenatally or later due to severe head trauma.

While numerous studies have consistently established the heritability of ADHD, there is growing recognition of the significant role of environmental influences in its manifestation. Thapar and Cooper (2016) and Posner, Polanczyk, and Sonuga-Barke (2020) emphasized that gene–environment interactions may constitute a primary pathway through which environmental exposures elevate the risk of developing ADHD. This highlights the need for a multifactorial approach in understanding and addressing this disorder.

ADHD has gained global recognition; however, misconceptions and a lack of awareness persist in Nigeria, where traditional beliefs, limited teacher training, and inadequate resources hinder diagnosis and intervention. For instance, Bakare, Ebigbo, and Ubochi (2016) highlighted that misconceptions about the causes of ADHD contribute to delayed diagnosis and treatment. The co-occurrence of ADHD with learning disabilities adds a layer of complexity to its management, necessitating a comprehensive approach that considers individual, cultural, and systemic factors.

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ADHD is primarily characterized by three core symptoms: inattention, impulsivity, and hyperactivity (Lin, Chang, Huang, Kuo, & Chiu, 2023; Khamenkan & Homchampa, 2024). According to Khamenkan and Homchampa (2024), children exhibiting inattention often demonstrate a short attention span, poor self-discipline, forgetfulness, and lack of diligence. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2019), such children are easily distracted, struggle to remain focused or complete tasks, appear not to listen, are frequently disorganized, procrastinate, and often misplace personal belongings.

Impulsivity is associated with behaviours such as hot-headedness, impatience, aggression, and a general lack of caution. The World Health Organization (WHO) (2019) notes that impulsive children may act without thinking, have difficulty waiting their turn, interrupt conversations, blurt out answers prematurely, intrude on others, or use items without permission.

Hyperactivity is the third defining feature of ADHD. Children with hyperactive tendencies are often described as restless, fidgety, excessively energetic, and constantly "on the go." They may talk excessively, have difficulty staying seated in structured settings such as classrooms, run or climb in inappropriate situations, and struggle to engage in quiet activities (WHO, 2019). These children are often unable to remain still for extended periods and may frequently experience accidents due to excessive physical activity, both at home and in school settings.

The understanding and management of ADHD differ across cultural and regional contexts and are often influenced by social norms, awareness, and available resources. The World Health Organization (2019) revealed that the symptoms of ADHD are not the same among all children. The condition can range from mostly poor attention to mostly hyperactivity and impulsivity or a combination of both. Bhattarai et al. (2020) observed that boys tend to be more hyperactive and girls tend to be quietly inattentive. Furthermore, Rimal and Pokharel (2016) revealed that the prevalence of ADHD among school-aged children is 11.7%, with males accounting for 80.5% and females accounting for 19.5%. Thomas, Sanders, Doust, Beller, and Glasziou (2015) postulated that ADHD is recognized globally as a significant contributor to academic and behavioural difficulties among children, with prevalence rates ranging from 5% to 7% in school-aged populations. ADHD can pose challenges in conventional school settings. In agreement with this view, Lasisi, Cornelius, Victor, Sheikh, and Omigbodun (2017) posited that ADHD is a common childhood neurodevelopmental disorder that is often associated with disturbed classroom behaviour.

Given the prevalence of ADHD, teachers are likely to have a child with ADHD in their classroom. Thus, Bolinger, Mucherah, and Markelz (2020) and Lin et al. (2023) assumed that teachers are likely to be among the first people to notice ADHD-related behaviours. However, Ogon (2017) and Olorunfemi and Odeunmi (2019) pointed out that teachers sometimes misinterpret ADHD symptoms as behavioural issues arising from poor home training, laziness, or irresponsibility, which can result in the neglect and punishment of affected students. Wijerathna et al. (2023) pointed out that punishment does not improve the outcome of students with ADHD. Thus, Komolafe, John, and Sowunmi (2021) submitted that not all teachers can effectively cater for the needs of children with ADHD, but those who are trained with professional skills and knowledge can provide for their needs. Komolafe et al. (2021) argued that information about ADHD can influence teachers' behaviours and perceptions of the disorder, and Bolinger et al. (2020) confirmed that teachers' ADHD knowledge influences

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teaching behaviours. Their understanding and approach can significantly impact academic performance, social development, and self-esteem. How many teachers are aware of ADHD?

Awareness refers to understanding and knowledge of something. Teachers who are aware of ADHD can better support students with the condition in the school environment. Greater awareness can also help teachers feel more confident and motivated to educate children exhibiting ADHD symptoms (Bolinger et al., 2020). In their empirical studies, scholars have indicated varying levels of teachers' awareness of ADHD. International evidence underscores the same challenge. For example, in India, Shetty and Rai (2014) surveyed 312 primary school teachers and found that while a large majority (268 out of 312) had heard of ADHD, only about 9% had received any prior training on the disorder. Moreover, only 29% of the participants demonstrated a relatively good understanding of ADHD, while the rest showed poor to moderate knowledge. This pattern highlights that although awareness of ADHD's existence can be high, the depth of knowledge about its symptoms, subtypes, and management remains limited. Significantly, Shetty and Rai reported that training positively correlated with better knowledge.

Similarly, Bhattarai, Bhusal, and Jaishi (2020) found that most of the 77 primary school teachers in Rupandehi Municipality, Nepal, had at least heard of ADHD and could identify some of its more visible symptoms (such as hyperactivity or difficulty sustaining attention); however, over half of the respondents (55.84%) still demonstrated low overall awareness of ADHD. This low awareness was especially evident in areas that go beyond mere symptom recognition—for example, understanding the risk factors that contribute to ADHD, the different subtypes of the disorder (inattentive, hyperactive/impulsive, and combined), and evidence-based management strategies such as behavioural interventions, classroom accommodations, or referral processes. Lin et al. (2023) reported that teachers may be more aware of children with combined-type ADHD but have less awareness about the inattentive subtype.

In Nigeria, Komolafe, John, and Sowunmi (2021) investigated 120 preschool teachers in Owode Local Government Area, Ogun State, and found that early childhood educators' knowledge of ADHD was generally low, while their attitude toward children with ADHD was negative. This dual challenge of limited knowledge and unfavourable attitudes at the preschool level is particularly concerning because early childhood educators are often the first professionals to observe developmental or behavioural issues in young children. They stated that a lack of both understanding and positive disposition can delay the identification of ADHD or lead to punitive rather than supportive responses, thereby undermining early intervention efforts. Since the preschool years are critical for laying the foundations of learning and socialization, the attitudes and competencies of these teachers can have a lasting impact on children with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder.

Expanding to the primary school context, Kennedy and Obumneke (2023) conducted a descriptive survey of 369 primary school teachers in the Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State and found that, while many teachers employed strategies to manage children with ADHD, gaps persisted in the consistency and effectiveness of these strategies. Their study reported no significant gender differences in the approaches adopted by teachers but highlighted that limited training and awareness still hinder optimal support for pupils with ADHD. They recommended targeted workshops and professional development programs to equip teachers

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and parents with evidence-based methods for managing ADHD behaviours in the classroom (Kennedy & Obumneke, 2023).

In an empirical study on inclusive education, Ogon (2017) found that targeted teacher training significantly enhances teachers' knowledge of ADHD and improves their capacity to identify and manage learners with ADHD in mainstream classrooms. Ogon further emphasized that without such training, many teachers in public and private schools tend to have a limited understanding of ADHD, which negatively affects classroom management and instructional effectiveness.

Despite these efforts, Dessie, Masresha, Bizuneh, and Daniel (2021) confirmed that studies on ADHD remain limited in sub-Saharan Africa, leading to gaps in addressing the unique challenges posed by the condition in educational environments. The few existing reports indicate an alarming rate at which ADHD is highly neglected in the region. According to Komolafe et al. (2021), a limited number of studies on teachers' awareness of ADHD in sub-Saharan Africa consistently report low levels of knowledge.

In Nigeria, students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) face unique challenges due to societal perceptions, a lack of awareness, and insufficient support systems in schools. Teachers may misunderstand the symptoms of ADHD, often attributing them to poor discipline or intentional defiance rather than recognizing the clinical nature of the disorder (Kennedy & Obumneke, 2023). This misunderstanding creates barriers to early diagnosis, appropriate intervention, and supportive learning environment development. Furthermore, cultural stigmatization often prevents families from seeking medical or psychological help, worsening the challenges faced by children with ADHD (Adetunji et al., 2019).

The educational implications of ADHD are profound, particularly in classrooms within the LGA of Rivers State, Port Harcourt. Similar to many other areas in Nigeria, this area is characterized by overburdened educational systems, undertrained teachers, and limited access to specialized resources (Ekechukwu & Nwobodo, 2018). Teachers in public and private schools often lack the necessary training to identify ADHD symptoms or implement effective teaching strategies for affected students. As a result, students with ADHD may struggle to meet academic expectations, experience low self-esteem, and face exclusionary disciplinary measures that further marginalize them and restrict their access to meaningful learning opportunities.

Teachers who know ADHD can recognize early signs and guide students toward appropriate interventions. Furthermore, teachers can adapt classroom strategies, such as seating arrangements, frequent breaks, clear instructions, and positive reinforcement, to accommodate students with ADHD. Thus, teachers can help children with ADHD function better and feel less frustrated. However, without proper awareness, teachers are less likely to implement strategies that accommodate the needs of students with ADHD, perpetuating cycles of academic underachievement and behavioural issues. Therefore, it is expedient to have an insight on secondary school teachers' awareness of ADHD. It is against this background that this study was concerned.

Statement of the problem

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is one of the most common learning disabilities affecting school-aged children. Its impact on society is enormous in terms of financial cost, stress to families, negative effects on self-esteem, and adverse academic and vocational outcomes. Children with ADHD can be recognized in clinics, schools, and homes. Their inattention leads to daydreaming, distractibility, and difficulties in

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sustaining effort on a single task for a prolonged period. Their impulsivity makes them accident prone, creates problems with peers, and disrupts classrooms. Furthermore, hyperactivity, often manifested as fidgeting and excessive talking, is poorly tolerated in schools and frustrates parents, who can easily lose them in crowds and cannot get them to sleep at a reasonable hour.

When ADHD goes unrecognized and unmanaged, it often results in low self-esteem, strained peer relationships, chronic academic underachievement, and behavioural problems that persist into adolescence and adulthood. ADHD poses challenges in conventional school settings. Children with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder often exhibit symptoms such as forgetfulness, excessive talking, fidgeting, and difficulty following through on tasks in the classroom. Therefore, children with ADHD need guidance and understanding from teachers to reach their full potential and succeed.

Although extensive research has been conducted in western contexts to understand ADHD and develop effective intervention strategies, a notable dearth of empirical studies addressing the disorder has been found within developing countries, particularly in Nigeria. In Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State, anecdotal evidence suggests that many teachers and parents do not understand ADHD. Symptoms are frequently misconstrued as signs of disobedience, laziness, or poor upbringing rather than as indicators of a diagnosable neurodevelopmental disorder. This misperception creates significant barriers to early identification and intervention, leaving many students without the support they need (Bakare et al., 2016; Kennedy & Obumneke 2023).

The diagnosis of ADHD is mainly clinical, and the history of the child's early development provided by the parents and teachers is the basis upon which the diagnosis is made. (Ching'oma, Mkoka, Ambikile, and Iseselo 2022). Therefore, the awareness of teachers regarding ADHD is crucial in diagnosing and referring children with suggestive symptoms of ADHD. The foregoing prompted the following question: What is the level of awareness of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among secondary school teachers in the Port Harcourt Local Government Area (LGA)? Providing an answer to this question poses the problem of this study.

Objectives of the study

The main purpose of this study is to examine the awareness level of ADHD among secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. To determine the extent to which secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA recognize ADHD-associated inattentive symptoms among secondary school students.
2. To investigate the extent to which secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA perceive impulsivity as a behavioural characteristic of students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder.
3. Examine the extent to which secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA understand hyperactivity as a core symptom of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent do secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA recognize inattentive symptoms associated with ADHD among secondary school students?

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2. To what extent do secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA perceive impulsivity as a behavioural characteristic of students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder?

3. To what extent do secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA understand hyperactivity as a core symptom of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

1. No significant difference was found in the mean responses of junior and senior secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA regarding the extent to which they recognized inattentive symptoms associated with ADHD.

2. No significant difference was found in the mean responses of junior and senior secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA regarding the extent to which they perceived impulsivity as a behavioural characteristic of students with ADHD.

3. No significant difference was found in the mean responses of junior and senior secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA regarding the extent to which they understood hyperactivity as a core symptom of ADHD.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study population consisted of 3,045 teachers, including 1,305 teachers of public senior secondary schools and 1,740 teachers of public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt LGA (Source: Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board and Rivers State Universal Basic Education Board, 2025). A sample size of 341 respondents was obtained using the Taro Yamene formula for determination of minimum sample size. The sample size was selected using a stratified sampling technique. Data were gathered through an instrument titled "Awareness of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder Questionnaire (ADHDQ)". The instrument was validated by test expert and guidance, and counselling experts, while the measure of stability was measured using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). Its reliability was established at 0.83 using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) to ascertain its reliability, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.83. Out of 341 questionnaires distributed to the respondents, 330 were retrieved and used for the study; the questionnaire contained demographic information and had 15 items that were in line with the study objectives. Responses were rated on a 4-point scale: high (4 points), moderate (3 points), low (2 points), and very low (1 point). The collected data were analysed using mean and standard deviation, with a benchmark of 2.50 to answer the research question. Hypotheses were tested using independent t-tests. The decision rule was to reject the null hypothesis if the t-calculated value was greater than the t-critical value otherwise accept.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent do secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA recognize inattentive symptoms associated with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) among secondary school students?

Table 1: Mean responses of secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA on the extent to which they recognize ADHD-associated inattentive symptoms among secondary school students.

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S/N	Item	Senior Sec. School (N=154)			Junior Sec. School (N=176)		
		Mean	SD	Rmk.	Mean	SD	Rmk.
1.	I am aware that students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder often have difficulty paying attention to details, resulting in careless mistakes.	1.97	0.86	LL	1.79	0.56	LL
2.	I am aware that students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder struggle to sustain attention during tasks or activities.	1].87	0.57	LL	1.90	0.63	LL
3.	I am aware that students with ADHD may appear to not listen when spoken to directly.	1.80	0.67	LL	1.91	0.85	LL
4.	I am aware that students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder often have difficulty completing tasks or following instructions	1.67	0.54	LL	1.92	0.65	LL
5.	I am aware that students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder frequently forget daily routines and activities.	2.03	0.77	LL	1.97	0.93	LL
Grand Mean		1.87	0.67	LL	1.90	0.72	LL

Source: Field survey conducted in 2025

Table 1 presents the mean responses of junior and senior secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA on the extent to which they recognize inattentive symptoms associated with ADHD among secondary school students. The results indicate that all mean scores fall below the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating that public secondary school teachers have a low level of awareness concerning inattention.

Research Question 2: To what extent do secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA perceive impulsivity as a behavioural characteristic of students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder?

Table 2: Mean responses of secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA on the extent to which they perceive impulsivity as a behavioural characteristic of students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder.

S/N	Item	Senior Sec. School (N=154)			Junior Sec. School (N=176)		
		Mean	SD	Rmk.	Mean	SD	Rmk.

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		Mean	SD	Rmk.	Mean	SD	Rmk.
1.	I am aware that students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder often have difficulty waiting their turn during games or group activities.	1.89	0.88	LL	1.86	0.58	LL
2.	I am aware that students with ADHD may leave their seats in situations where they are expected to remain seated.	1.81	0.59	LL	1.90	0.75	LL
3.	I am aware that students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder frequently interrupt conversations or intrude on others.	1.73	0.59	LL	1.82	0.74	LL
4.	I am aware that students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder may express feelings of inner restlessness or agitation.	1.66	0.51	LL	1.82	0.67	LL
5.	I am aware that students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder often struggle with self-control and patiently	1.99	0.71	LL	1.98	0.79	LL
Grand Mean		1.82	0.66	LL	1.88	0.71	LL

Source: Field survey conducted in 2025

Table 2 presents the mean responses of junior and secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA on the extent to which they perceive impulsivity as a behavioural characteristic of students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. The results indicate that all mean scores fall below the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating a low level of impulsivity awareness among public secondary school teachers.

Research Question 3: To what extent do secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA understand hyperactivity as a core symptom of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder?

Table 3: Mean responses of secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA on the extent to which they understand hyperactivity as a core symptom of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder.

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S/N	Item	Senior Sec. School (N=154)			Junior Sec. School (N=176)		
		Mean	SD	Rmk.	Mean	SD	Rmk.
1.	I am aware that students with ADHD often fidget when seated.	1.94	0.87	LL	1.84	0.69	LL
2.	I am aware that students with ADHD may find it difficult to engage in quiet play or activities.	1.90	0.58	LL	2.07	0.79	LL
3.	I am aware that students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder may blurt out answers before a question is fully asked.	1.81	0.57	LL	2.02	0.77	LL
4.	I am aware that students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder tend to talk excessively, even in inappropriate contexts.	1.69	0.59	LL	1.91	0.72	LL
5.	I am aware that students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder frequently squirm in their seats or display constant movement.	2.08	0.81	LL	2.01	0.84	LL
Grand Mean		1.88	0.68	LL	1.97	0.76	LL

Source: Field survey conducted in 2025

Table 3 displays the mean responses of junior and senior secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA on the extent to which they understood hyperactivity as a core symptom of ADHD. The findings reveal that all mean scores are below the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating that public secondary school teachers in the area demonstrate a low level of hyperactivity-related behaviour awareness.

Hypothesis 1

No significant difference was found in the mean responses of junior and senior secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA regarding the extent to which they recognized inattentive symptoms associated with ADHD.

Table 4: T-test summary showing the difference in mean response scores between junior and senior secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA on the extent to which they recognize inattentive symptoms associated with ADHD.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal.	t-crit	Decision
Junior School	176	1.90	.32	328	.70	1.96	Accept
Senior Sec. School	154	1.87	.38				

Source: Field survey conducted in 2025

Table 4 presents the t-test summary showing the difference in the mean response scores of senior and junior secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA regarding their level of awareness of inattention. The result reveals that the calculated t-value (0.70) is less than the critical t-value (1.96) at the significance level of 0.05 with 328 degrees of freedom. Based on this result, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating no significant difference in the mean response scores of junior and senior public secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA regarding their awareness of inattention symptoms.

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Hypothesis 2

No significant difference was found in the mean responses of junior and senior secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA regarding the extent to which they perceived impulsivity as a behavioural characteristic of students with ADHD.

Table 5: t-test summary showing the difference in mean response scores between junior and senior secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA on the extent to which they perceive impulsivity as a behavioural characteristic of students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal.	t-crit	Decision
Junior School	176	1.81	.34	328	1.52	1.96	Accept
Senior Sec. School	154	1.87	.37				

Source: Field survey conducted in 2025

Table 5 displays the t-test summary comparing the mean response scores of senior and junior secondary school teachers on their level of impulsivity awareness. The analysis shows that the calculated t-value (1.52) is less than the critical t-value (1.96) at the significance level of 0.05 with 328 degrees of freedom. Consequently, the null hypothesis is upheld, indicating no significant difference in the mean awareness scores of senior and junior public secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA with respect to impulsivity as a behavioural characteristic of ADHD.

Hypothesis 3

No significant difference was found in the mean responses of junior and senior secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA regarding the extent to which they understood hyperactivity as a core symptom of ADHD.

Table 6: t-test summary showing the difference in mean response scores between junior and senior secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA on the extent to which they understand hyperactivity as a core symptom of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal.	t-crit	Decision
Junior School	176	1.97	.37	328	2.07	1.96	Reject
Senior Sec. School	154	1.89	.37				

Source: Field survey conducted in 2025

Table 6 shows the t-test summary for the difference in mean response scores of senior and junior secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA regarding their hyperactivity awareness level. The calculated t-value (2.07) exceeded the critical t-value (1.96) at the 0.05 level of significance with 328 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating a significant difference in the mean response scores of senior and junior public secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA concerning their awareness of hyperactivity-related ADHD symptoms.

Discussion

The first major finding of this study relates to teachers’ recognition of ADHD-associated inattention symptoms. As presented in Table 1, the grand mean scores for senior secondary school teachers (M = 1.87, SD = 0.67) and junior secondary school teachers (M = 1.90, SD = 0.72) both fell within the “Low Level” (LL) range. This indicates that teachers in Port Harcourt LGA generally lack sufficient awareness of inattentive behaviours such

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as difficulty sustaining attention, frequent distractibility, failing to complete tasks or appearing not to listen when spoken to directly. The independent-samples t-test (Table 4) showed no statistically significant difference between the two groups ($t\text{-cal} = 0.70 < t\text{-crit} = 1.96, df = 328$), suggesting that this low awareness of inattention is consistent across senior and junior secondary school teachers. This finding is consistent with that of Lin et al. (2023), who reported that teachers often possess limited knowledge about the inattentive subtype of ADHD, which may hinder early identification and appropriate intervention. It also aligns with Komolafe, Adeyemo, and Olowookere (2021), who observed that teachers' general awareness of ADHD in Nigerian schools remains significantly low, particularly with regard to recognizing subtle behavioural indicators such as inattention. This outcome also corroborates Ogon's (2017) assertions that a lack of proper understanding may lead teachers to incorrectly interpret students with inattention symptoms as disinterested or unmotivated rather than recognize them as learners with a neurodevelopmental challenge.

Therefore, the pattern observed in the present study indicates that this lack of awareness could contribute to the under-identification of students with ADHD and a corresponding delay in providing necessary support.

Second, the study found that teachers' perception of impulsivity as a behavioural characteristic of ADHD is low. Specifically, senior secondary school teachers recorded a grand mean score of 1.82 ($SD = 0.66$), whereas junior secondary school teachers recorded a grand mean score of 1.88 ($SD = 0.71$) on the impulsivity awareness scale. According to the decision rule of the instrument, these values (rated "LL"–low level) indicate that both groups of teachers have limited knowledge of impulsive behaviours associated with ADHD. The t-test result ($t\text{-cal} = 1.52 < t\text{-crit} = 1.96, df = 328$) shows no statistically significant difference between the two groups, suggesting that the low level of awareness is consistent across senior and junior secondary school teachers.

This finding aligns with Bhattarai et al.'s (2020) observation that teachers in developing countries generally exhibit low levels of awareness regarding the impulsive and hyperactive features of ADHD. It is also consistent with the findings of Komolafe, Adeyemo, and Olowookere (2021), who reported that studies in sub-Saharan Africa revealed a pervasive lack of knowledge among teachers about the behavioural subtypes of ADHD. This study further highlights that teachers in the Port Harcourt Local Government Area also demonstrate a limited ability to distinguish impulsive behaviours linked to ADHD from ordinary classroom misconduct. This lack of distinction may lead to inappropriate disciplinary measures, mislabelling, or delayed intervention, thereby undermining the provision of effective support for students with disabilities (Kennedy & Obumneke 2023).

The third finding revealed a generally low level of understanding of hyperactivity as a core symptom of ADHD among the respondents. As shown in Table 3, the grand mean scores for both senior secondary ($M = 1.88, SD = 0.68$) and junior secondary teachers ($M = 1.97, SD = 0.76$) fell within the "Low Level" range, indicating that most teachers had limited understanding of hyperactivity as a core symptom of ADHD. Teachers consistently demonstrated low awareness across all five indicators, such as fidgeting with hands or feet ($M = 1.94, SD = 0.87$ for senior; $M = 1.84, SD = 0.69$ for junior), difficulty engaging in quiet activities ($M = 1.90, SD = 0.58; M = 2.07, SD = 0.79$), and excessive talking ($M = 1.69, SD = 0.59; M = 1.91, SD = 0.72$). The independent-samples t-test (Table 6) further showed a statistically significant difference between junior ($M = 1.97, SD =$

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0.37) and senior secondary teachers ($M = 1.89$, $SD = 0.37$), $t(328) = 2.07$, $p < .05$, suggesting that junior secondary school teachers displayed slightly higher awareness than their senior secondary counterparts.

This finding has important implications. It indicates that teachers in secondary school students in Port Harcourt LGA may misinterpret overt symptoms such as restlessness, fidgeting, or difficulty remaining seated as signs of indiscipline, laziness, or misconduct. Such misunderstanding can lead to inappropriate labelling and ineffective classroom responses. Olorunfemi and Odebunmi (2019) support this view, noting that in many Nigerian schools, ADHD-related behaviours are frequently misclassified as deliberate misbehaviour rather than as manifestations of a neurodevelopmental condition.

The pattern of responses shown in this study is reflected in the reported standard deviations across all three domains. The item-level SDs reported in Tables 1–3 are higher because they reflect variability on each individual question, whereas the SDs in Tables 4–6 are smaller because they use aggregated mean scores for the t-tests. When multiple items are combined, extreme responses tend to cancel out, resulting in smaller SD values. This consistent pattern reinforces the conclusion that the low levels of awareness observed in this study are not random but widespread trends across both senior and junior secondary school teachers. Taken together, these findings underscore the urgent need for targeted teacher training and professional development programs that focus on ADHD awareness, early identification, and effective classroom management strategies.

Conclusion

The findings of this study indicate a generally low level of awareness of ADHD among public secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt LGA, particularly in relation to the core symptoms of inattention, impulsivity, and hyperactivity. The mean scores across all indicators were consistently below the criterion benchmark, indicating limited teacher recognition of ADHD-related behaviours. This lack of awareness poses a significant challenge to early identification and appropriate classroom support for affected learners.

Furthermore, the results of the independent t-test analyses provide deeper insight into the differences in awareness levels between junior and senior secondary school teachers. No significant differences were found in their awareness of inattention and impulsivity, indicating a uniformly low awareness across both educational levels. However, a significant difference was observed in their awareness of hyperactivity, indicating that senior and junior secondary teachers may perceive or interpret hyperactive behaviours differently.

These findings underscore the critical need for targeted professional development and in-service training programs that address the identification and management of ADHD symptoms in classroom settings. Equipping teachers with adequate knowledge and practical strategies is essential for creating inclusive learning environments and ensuring that students with ADHD are not mislabelled or excluded from meaningful educational participation. In collaboration with teachers and administrators, the school counsellor must take a leading role in promoting awareness, early intervention, and supportive practices that enhance the academic and socio-emotional well-being of all learners.

Recommendations

1. The government should conduct an awareness training programmes on ADHD to school teachers to achieve sufficient competency to recognize children with ADHD and classroom management techniques to create an enabling and encouraging environment for children with ADHD to achieve their educational goals.

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2. The government should provide a National School Health programmes to cater for mental and behavioural disorders in schools so that affected children would have more opportunities to be referred to specialists.

3. School authorities should collaborate with school counsellors and health care professionals to better understand ADHD and tailor support strategies for students.

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